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**ASSESSMENT OF SOCIOECONOMIC
VULNERABILITY & EFFECTIVE
MANAGEMENT OF FLOOD IN KANDI BLOCK,
MURSHIDABAD**

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ABSTRACT :

Kandi is situated in the Mayurakshi Stream bowl. The region is depleted by three primary waterway frameworks: the Mayurakshi-Bele, the Brahmani-Dwarka, and the Bakreshwar-Kopai-Kuye. In this topic “Assessment Of Socioeconomic Vulnerability & Effective Management Of Flood In Kandi Block, Murshidabad” Every one of the three frameworks consolidate into one lastly stream into the Bhagirathi Waterway through the Babla-Uttarasan framework. The socioeconomic vulnerability of the community to comprehend their exposure and coping mechanisms regarding the flood hazard and the Recommend effective management strategies, incorporating both structural and non-structural approaches, to mitigate the impact of future floods and enhance resilience in the affected area. These waterway frameworks convey enormous releases during storm season, causing boundless flooding and seepage blockage in Kandi and bordering regions, as a large portion of the many years old dikes are in run down conditions. During floods, the region can be completely cut off from different pieces of the locale for a really long time, making the vehicle of help materials and quick departure testing. In 2015, the normal yearly harm created by these issues.

KEY WORDS : *Physical and Cultural Variation, Kandi Block, Murshidabad District, Socioeconomic Vulnerability, Effective Management*

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INTRODUCTION:

Kandi is a sub-divisional city and municipality in Murshidabad district in West Bengal, India. It is the headquarters of the Kandi subdivision and is located on the east bank of Kana Mayurakshi River. The town is known for being one of the oldest municipal bodies in India, having acquired municipality status in 1869. Every year, many natural & humanistic disasters would happen at many different places of whole world. One of them Flood is a natural as well as unnatural disaster. It is an arena of study of hydrology, where flood is an overflow of water that liquidates land that is usually dry. They are the most common and widespread natural severe weather event. Flood can look very different because flooding covers anything from a few inches of water to several feet. There are mainly two types of causes of flooding like (i) physical (Prolonged rainfall, Snow melting, Strom surges), (ii) human (changes in land use, urbanise, climate change etc), which promote flooding most. The districts in the southern parts of the State namely the Gangetic West Bengal experience heavy precipitation particularly in the months of September and October consequently upon low

pressure/depressions developed in the Bay of Bengal during the major flood years 1956, 1959, 1978, 1995, 1999 and 2000. And Most flood affected districts of West Bengal are Hooghly, Howrah, Paschim Medinipur, Murshidabad. Flood-prone Regions of West Bengal Among the mostly affected districts, Murshidabad is most prominent due to its vulnerability and location. Almost each and every year this district suffers from flood and creates landforms common to flood prone regions. Kandi block of Murshidabad district, West Bengal is situated in the Mayurakshi- Dwarka Plain. This is one of the maximum flood-affected blocks in Murshidabad. The average frequency of occurrence of floods in the last decade is 8.

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SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

The study is important to understand flood as a natural disaster, Causes for the flood and its impact. It is important to know how a natural disaster affects the area likely the loss of life, property, flora and fauna and also mental disturbance. It also becomes important because flood is among the most frequent natural disaster that causes great economic losses for the studied area and it is important to understand the present situation for the existing flora and fauna, so to understand the importance of harmony with the nature is studied. The flood study can be used to determine the probability of an area of land being prone to flooding. It is also important for flood frequency analysis to relate the magnitude of extreme runoff or river flow events to their frequency of occurrence through the use of probability distribution functions. This study helps to understand the importance of disaster management strategies undertaken by the people and the government to face the disaster of flood. It will also helpful to the authorities, communities and organisation to make informed decisions significantly reducing the loss of life and property as well as to prevent any development or urbanisation into unsafe floodplains. Moreover, climate change is also contributing in the increase of the frequency of flood, therefore the study of flood became very important in present time.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

- **Das and Samanta (2022)**, Examined the impact of floods and river bank erosion on the people living along the Malda district. They used field measurements on data analysis technique to understand how these phenomena affect local people.
- **Sengupta, Nitish,(2011)**, According to, deficiency of farming area or useful land, the vast majority of individuals in this space lose their positions, which adversely affects their pay. Furthermore, movements to different puts because of work expectations. Stream disintegration significantly affects training
- **Hire Pramod Kumar S. and Kale Vishwas S. (2006)**, In this paper attempt has been made to quantitatively evaluate the geomorphic effectiveness of three large magnitude flood occurred in 1959,1968, and 1969 in the lower Tapi basin. Flood hydrographs of these and other flood events show that the duration of floods can range from 6 to 10 days, and in exceptional cases up to 15 days. Hence to produce substantial changes in the alluvial section of the Tapi river.
- **Department of Relief and Rehabilitation (2004)**, This report shows multi-disaster response plan which is including overview of Dhule district and Maharashtra flood report-2005.

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- **Singh Yadvinder (2000)**, He focused on flood affected area of interstate Chandigarh region, flood affected area during 1988 and 1983, ISCR- flood intensity of affected area- 1993.

PROBLEMS

LOSS OF LIVELIHOODS:

As communication links and infrastructure such as power plants, roads and bridges are damaged and disrupted, economic activities come to a standstill, resulting in dislocation and the dysfunction of normal life for a period much beyond the duration of the flooding.

DECREASED PURCHASING AND PRODUCTION POWER:

Damage to infrastructure also causes long-term impacts, such as disruptions to clean water and electricity, transport, communication, education and health care.

MASS MIGRATION:

Frequent flooding, resulting in loss of livelihoods, production and other prolonged economic impacts and types of suffering can trigger mass migration or population displacement.

EROSION:

Floods cause erosion because the amount of power that the flow of water brings is often sufficient enough to completely tear away top layers of soil.

PSYCHOSOCIAL EFFECTS:

The huge psycho-social effects on flood victims and their families can traumatize them for long periods of time. The loss of loved ones can generate deep impacts, especially on children. Hindering economic growth and development. The high cost of relief and recovery may adversely impact investment in infrastructure and other development activities in the area and in certain cases may cripple the frail economy of the region.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To know the socioeconomic vulnerability of the community to comprehend their exposure and coping mechanisms regarding the flood hazard.
2. To know to the Recommend effective management strategies, incorporating both structural and non-structural approaches, to mitigate the impact of future floods and enhance resilience in the affected area.

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RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the socioeconomic vulnerability of the community to comprehend their exposure and coping mechanisms regarding the flood hazard ?
2. What is the Recommend effective management strategies, incorporating both structural and non-structural approaches, to mitigate the impact of future floods and enhance resilience in the affected area ?

METHODOLOGY:

The present study is mainly based on primary data collection which have been collected from Door -to -door Household survey (HHS) using structured and pre tested questionnaire. The quantity of rainwater and the frequency of heavy rainy days have been known by primary survey. We know about the irrigation system of the area which may be the causes of flood discussed with the local people. The geographical and the historical background of the study area helps us to know about the physical condition, nature of landscape, soil type, climatic condition etc. Through interaction, we understand the nature of flood, intensity of flood, the management system etc. The effect of flood on their lifestyle and also on their settlement, agricultural system got to know by consulting with the habitant. Also, some secondary data are used to complete the report and to come to a conclusion. We know about the past condition of the study area. The location and the characteristics of the settlement and the impact of it for flood have known from some secondary sources. For secondary data, we took help of some websites like (Water and Irrigation department), some journals, some reports etc.

LOCATION OF THE STUDY AREA:

Kandi is a municipality in the Murshidabad district of the state of West Bengal, India. It is located in the northeastern part of the district. The latitude of Kandi is 23° 95'' N and longitude is 88° 03' E. Kandi is approximately 200 km (124 miles) north of Kolkata, the capital city of West Bengal, and is well connected by road and rail to other parts of the state and country.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Kandi is the South-western Sub-division of the Murshidabad region, having all out topographical area of 1190 Sq K.M with a populace of 12.05 lakh, and containing five improvement blocks, to be specific Khargram, Burwan, Kandi, Bharatpur-I and Bharatpur-II. An area of around 510 Sq K.M comprising of whole Bharatpur-I, portions of Khargram, Burwan and Kandi blocks is basically inclined to ceaseless flood and seepage blockage and

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remain completely cut-off for a long time together from different pieces of the region during flood. The previously mentioned region is depleted by three principal waterway frameworks specifically, the Mayurakshi-Bele, the Brahmani-Dwarka and the Bakreshwar - Kopai - Kuye. Every one of the three frameworks consolidate into one lastly outfalls into the waterway Bhagirathi through the Babla - Uttarasan framework. The waterway frameworks portrayed above convey gigantic release during storm causing boundless flood and seepage blockage in Kandi and abutting regions as the majority of the dikes, developed many years prior through ex-zamindary or different sources, are in run down conditions. The interminable event of flood and waste blockage make untold wretchedness individuals. The typical yearly harm is to the tune of Rs. 97.55 Crore. Transport of alleviation materials and quick clearing of impacted individuals turns out to be truly difficult errand in such time.

PHYSICAL BACKGROUND: -

PHYSIOGRAPHY: -

The intermediate tract situated in the Indian territory that lies between Bhagirathi and Padma rivers and the location from which the great deltaic plain originated can be called Murshidabad. The Bhagirathi River splits the district into two natural physiographic region- Rarh on west and Bagri on the east. Kandi subdivision lies in the Mayurakshi-Dwarka plain in South East corner of the Rarh region. This Rarh region is continuation of Sub-Vindhyan region composed of laterite clay. The altitude of this land is slightly high and undulating in nature.

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TOPOGRAPHY: -

Kandi block is in the Mayurakshi Dwaraka plain and is situated in the south- eastern corner of the Rarh region in Murshidabad district. This Rarh region is continuation of Sub-Vindhyan region composed of clay. This area lies in the upper deltaic region.

The area is characterized by undulating terrain with mostly lateritic clay. The altitude of this area is slightly high and undulating in nature. This block is situated at an average height of 20 metres above the mean sea level. In this region the slope is comparatively high in the northern part than the southern part. The average slope is 3.5% in the northern part and 1.5% in the southern part of the study area.

CLIMATE: -

Climate refers to the long-term pattern of weather in a particular area. Climate plays an important role in determining the basic needs like types of foods, clothing and shelter, occupations, etc.

Kandi is a sub-divisional city and municipality in Murshidabad district in West Bengal, India. It experiences a sub-tropical climate, characterized by hot summers, monsoon rains and mild winters. Summer (March to June): Summers are hot and humid, with temperatures typically ranging from 27°C to 41°C. It can get quite uncomfortable during this time, especially in the peak summer months of April and May. Monsoon (June to September): The majority of its rainfall during the monsoon season. The south-west monsoon brings heavy rainfall, which can sometimes lead to flooding in low-lying areas. The highest amount of precipitation occurs during the month of July, with an average quantity up to 339 mm. Humidity remains high during this time. Each year, there is an approximate 1401 mm of precipitation that occurs. Winter (October to February): Winters are mild and pleasant, with temperatures ranging from 10°C to 24°C. Mostly dry and cool. In Kandi, the average annual temperature is an approximate 16.2°C & 61.2°F. It is the most comfortable time to visit Kandi. Overall, Kandi experiences a typical Indian sub-continental climate with distinct seasonal variations.

DRAINAGE: -

Kandi is located in the Mayurakshi River basin. The area is drained by three main river systems: the Mayurakshi-Bele, the Brahmani-Dwarka, and the Bakreshwar – Kopai - Kuye. All the three systems combine into one and finally flow into the Bhagirathi River through the Babla-Uttarasan system. These river systems carry huge discharges during monsoon season, causing wide spread flooding and drainage congestion Kandi and adjoining areas, as most of

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the decades old embankments are in dilapidated conditions. During floods, the area can be totally cut off from other parts of the district for days, making the transport of relief materials and rapid evacuation challenging.

SOIL: -

Kandi subdivision lies in the Mayurakshi Dwaraka plain in south-eastern corner of the Rarh region. The Rarh region is undulating and contains mostly clay and lateritic clay- based soil. Laterite soil is rich in aluminium and iron, formed in wet and hot tropical areas. It is prepared by the long-lasting and intensive weathering of the parent rock.

SOCIO – ECONOMIC BACKGROUND: -

DEMOGRAPHY: -

According to the 2011 census of India, Kandi had a total population of 55,632 of which 28,442 (51%) were males and 27,190 (49%) were females. Population in the age range 0-6 years was 5,889. The total number of literate persons in Kandi was 40,816 (82.05% of the population over 6 years). As of the 2001 census of India, Kandi had a population of 50,345. Males constitute 53% of the population and females 47%. Kandi has an average literacy rate of 65%, higher than the national average of 59.5%: male literacy is 70%, and female literacy is 60%. In Kandi, 14% of the population is under 6 years of age.

AGE-SEX COMPOSITION:

Age-sex composition shows the male and female distribution of a particular area. Here, 5 villages of Kandi, Murshidabad have been put together to prepare this age- sex structure. We can see the female percentage of <10 age group is very high (30.6%) as compare to male (16.2%), and also in the highest age group >60 female percentage is higher (8.1%) than male (4.6%). Though in the working population age group (21 to 60) the male population is high. So, it shows a good balance in the age-sex structure of Kandi.

AGE - SEX COMPOSITION

SEX RATIO:

There is quite a balanced distribution in the male and female population. So, the sex ratio is also representable. The male population is higher (53.1%) than female (46.9%). It shows that there is not a very large difference in the sex ratio.

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CASTE COMPOSITION:

Kandi has different caste categories. Among them SC category is very much noticed (56.6%), followed by OBC-A (35.8%), General (5.7%), and ST (1.9%). It means huge population belongs to SC category.

Elements	Socioeconomic Vulnerability (%)	Recommend Effective (%)
People	65.32	22.32
Animal	58.21	21.65
House	36.21	10.21
Agricultural Land	45.21	36.21
Food Crop	54.21	32.25
Road	38.32	12.32
Industry	25.21	13.32

<i>socioeconomic vulnerability (%)</i>		<i>Recommend effective (%)</i>	
Mean	46.09857143	Mean	21.18286
Standard Error	5.294555347	Standard Error	3.812843
Median	45.21	Median	21.65
Mode	#N/A	Mode	#N/A

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Standard Deviation	14.00807675	Standard Deviation	10.08783
Sample Variance	196.2262143	Sample Variance	101.7644
Kurtosis	-0.964684864	Kurtosis	-1.32251
Skewness	-0.096836101	Skewness	0.510719
Range	40.11	Range	26
Minimum	25.21	Minimum	10.21
Maximum	65.32	Maximum	36.21
Sum	322.69	Sum	148.28
Count	7	Count	7
Confidence Level(95.0%)	12.95531023	Confidence Level(95.0%)	9.32969

IMPACT:

- ❖ A flood can be defined as the overflow of large amounts of water beyond the prescribed limits. Trading can have a major impact, such as it can lead to various communicable disease, damage the infrastructure and property, damage any plants or wildlife that come in its birth and contaminate habitats. In some cases, Local residents may even be killed or injured. The impact of flooding is determined by flood depth, The rate at which an area is inundated, options for evacuation, economic value, and

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- the number of residents. The Impact of flooding can differ from one sector to the next. Some of the effects of the flood occurring in the region are-
- ❖ Floods have been responsible for some of history's deadliest disasters. Flood waters, particularly sewer floods, can spread diseases such as cholera in addition to being direct causes of death. The subsequent destruction of infrastructure restricts the supply of safe drinking water. Minor floods can cause moulds and mildew to grow in homes, causing respiratory illness in some people. Another significant risk is the psychological impact of flooding. One of the most significant impacts of flood is the damage to, and destruction of homes and personal belongings.
 - ❖ Floods have the power to topple homes and buildings in some cases, and electricity can be cut off. When flood waters remain and block roads or other modes of transportation, it becomes much more difficult to rescue people and bring supplies. Boats and helicopters are frequently used to assist people trapped in flood-damaged areas. The damage can last long after the flood waters recede; homes flooded by even a centimetre of water may require costly repairs. Water and moisture damage the foundations of buildings and structural components, necessitating inspection and repairs to ensure their safety.
 - ❖ Flood damages any plants or wildlife that come in its path and contaminate habitats. Pathogens and algae can contaminate the local water supply, destroying groundwater quality. On the other hand, flooding isn't all bad because the sediment from the floods can help replenish nutrients in the soil, improving plant growth. While flooding can contaminate groundwater, it is also critical to assist in replenishing groundwater supplies. Also, flood helps to replenish wetland environments that have become too dry. On Economy- Flood can have huge economy repercussions to the region, as extreme weather events impact key, notably agriculture, fishing, food crops, health, labour and tourism. Studies have found that frequent flooding could shave 11% of the regions GDP by the end of the century. Economic hardship due to a temporary decline in tourism, rebuilding costs, or food shortages leading to price increases is a common after -effect of severe flooding. Other Impacts- The secondary impact of floods can be the contamination of floodwaters with chemicals and sewage. This can pose a threat to the health of people and animals and can increase the risk of contracting waterborne diseases. In the agricultural sector, flooding can ruin crops, delay harvests, spoil produce, remove or contaminate valuable topsoil and cause death of livestock. These impacts can cause great emotional stress and financial loss to farmers. Female percentage is higher than the male percentage in both younger and older age groups. Though the male population is high in the age group of working population. This shows an approximately balanced structure of age-sex composition

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in Kandi. A huge amount of population belongs to SC category, the area is dominated by the Muslims and the married people are found most. The majority have the primary standard education and the higher education level is very low in this area. Most of the people are engaged in primary activity as farmers. Most of the household's monthly income is between 10000-20000. According to most of the households, the area was flooded more than 6 times and the flood leads to significant damage to agricultural land and the drinking water of this area, with loss of animals and property. Continuous rainfall is found as the main cause of flood. But low level of preparedness is observed among the people. Most of the houses are semi-pucca. People need to leave their houses during flood and they are not fully prepared for future flood. There is also a lack of facility given by the government and any other special forces.

THE OBSERVED FINDINGS NEED SOME REMEDIES -

Firstly, basic awareness about flood is to be spread among the people so that they can face the future disaster. They also should build their houses as far as possible from the river. Besides this, disaster preparedness training, early warning systems are to be improved. Medical facilities should be enhanced. Erosion is to be controlled in sustainable ways and water management is to be improved. The Government and the NGOs also should strengthen their actions to mitigate these issues.

- Bank line moving expands the gamble of waterway bank disintegration in weak regions across the stream. Because of consistent stream disintegration, the towns along the waterway are totally washed away. Stream disintegration in Samsanganj is more regular during storm and post-rainstorm.

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- Bank line moving of stream Ganga is the primary driver of waterway disintegration. Presently the bank line moving of stream Ganga is more towards left side than right side thus waterway disintegration is being noticed surprisingly in left side.
- Consistently, how much dregs that is taken out from the stream bed is increasingly more residue is put away in the waterway bed, subsequently the water holding limit of the stream diminishes and individuals living on the bank line are in harm's way.
- Proceed with stream bank disintegration and movement are significant elements in changing the regular highlights of this area, vegetation, farming area, water body, muddy land.
- Because of the deficiency of farming area or useful land, the vast majority of individuals in this space lose their positions, which adversely affects their pay. Furthermore, movements to different puts because of work expectations. Stream disintegration significantly affects training.
- Denied of training in disintegration region, numerous youngster workers are seen here who are generally engaged with Beddi moving work.

CONCLUSION

After the conversation in past part connected with stream bank disintegration causes and effect in Samsrganj block of Murshidabad Area. Waterway bank disintegration is a whiz peculiarity that can make huge harm settlements and foundation close to streams. It is brought about by a assortment of variables, including human exercises and regular processes.

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The effects of stream bank disintegration can be extreme, counting loss of property and foundation, removal of networks, and ecological debasement. Notwithstanding, by going to lengths to relieve the impacts of disintegration, for example, building defensive designs and executing feasible land use rehearses, we can limit its effect and safeguard individuals, foundation, and the climate. It is fundamental for states and networks to cooperate to address stream bank disintegration and guarantee the long haul maintainability of settlements close to waterways.

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